

Utility-Driven Adaptive Model Selection for Digital Twinning

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Abstract

Digital twins have become central to modern engineering by providing interconnected virtual representations that mirror the behavior of physical assets. Their effectiveness, however, depends critically on the fidelity and efficiency of the underlying computational models used for decision support. This work introduces an adaptive Bayesian framework for quantifying and optimizing the fidelity, efficiency, and overall utility of such virtual representations when approximating system responses in decision-oriented contexts. By integrating reduced-order models (ROMs) within a Bayesian inference and decision-theoretic setting, the framework identifies, at any point in time, the lowest-cost model capable of delivering the required predictive accuracy across all quantities of interest, while rigorously accounting for the uncertainty associated with each model resolution. The approach maximizes an expected-utility function that balances two competing attributes: (i) precision, reflecting the effect of over- or under-estimating target quantities on decision quality, and (ii) computational efficiency, ensuring feasibility for real-time inference. Leveraging continuously assimilated monitoring data, the framework performs this model selection recursively, enabling the virtual twin to evolve in tandem with the physical system. The resulting methodology supports automated decisions on whether to retain the current model, switch to an alternative resolution, or trigger retraining—thus establishing a pathway toward adaptive, trustworthy digital twins for engineering decision support.

Keywords: Digital Twinning, Reduced Order Models (ROMs), Bayesian Model Updating, Bayesian Inference, uncertainty quantification

1. Introduction

2 Infrastructure assets are inherently complex, featuring large-scale models, nonlinear dynamics, and considerable
3 uncertainty. As next-generation systems come to the forefront, there is a clear shift toward digital and hybrid twin
4 representations that provide virtual counterparts of physical assets [1, 2]. The process of creating these representa-
5 tions—commonly referred to as virtualization or twinning—aims to replicate and interact with the behavior of real
6 systems [3, 4]. To ensure such virtual assets operate effectively, they must rely on computational models that are both
7 accurate and efficient [5]. Without this balance, real-time applications central to Operations and Management (O&M),
8 Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), and decision support become infeasible [6, 7].

9 In the existing literature, numerous frameworks aim to develop low-dimensional models or numerical surrogates
10 that enable rapid computation while retaining the essential physics of high-fidelity systems [8, 9, 10]. Broadly, these
11 approaches fall into two categories: data-driven methods and physics-aware methodologies. Data-driven models are
12 particularly effective for systems with complex or chaotic dynamics [11, 12]. However, they often rely on ad hoc
13 training procedures that capture only limited input–output relationships and tend to degrade in performance under
14 environmental or parametric variability [13]. Moreover, such methods typically struggle to extrapolate across time,
15 input conditions, or spatial discretizations of the target system [14]. As a result, many data-driven surrogates remain
16 problem-specific, mesh-dependent, and unable to generalize beyond the variable used for training [15, 16]. These
17 limitations restrict their practicality for developing actionable digital models suitable for integration into higher-level
18 O&M, SHM, or decision-making frameworks.

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20 In contrast, physics-based and physics-aware approaches preserve the internal structure of the dynamical system
and embed physical knowledge through explicit constraints or inductive biases within the virtual model [17, 18].
22 This improves interpretability, stability, and accuracy in extrapolation and generalization tasks, thereby enhancing the
applicability and reliability of the resulting digital representations for higher-level engineering workflows [19]. The ef-
fectiveness of such strategies has been demonstrated in several studies, including [20] and its extension in [21], where
24 reduced-order models (ROMs) serve as forward simulators in inverse problem settings for fault detection and input
estimation in real time. Similarly, [22] employs stochastic ROMs for damage detection in a mock-up aircraft wing,
26 while [23] showcases the integration of ROMs with the Unscented Kalman Filter for system identification and uncer-
tainty quantification under environmental and parametric variability. Beyond model-based inference, related advances
28 using physics-informed surrogates have also emerged [24, 25, 26, 27, 28]. In this work, we focus on model-based
methodologies, which provide a structured, physics-grounded framework to support engineering decisions across the
30 operation and maintenance (O&M) life-cycle of infrastructure assets [29, 30]. The core of such frameworks lies in
numerical models that condense complex systems into computationally tractable forms while retaining their essential
32 dynamic behavior, variability, and uncertainty.

34 However, the usefulness of virtual models ultimately depends on balancing computational cost against model
fidelity, particularly when their outputs support high-stakes engineering decisions. Developing digital representations
that maintain this balance is inherently challenging, as achieving consistent efficiency without compromising accuracy
36 becomes increasingly difficult for evolving and data-rich systems [31]. In this work, we address this challenge through
an adaptive, data-informed framework that leverages continuous monitoring information to dynamically select the
38 most suitable model using Bayesian decision theory. By evaluating a hierarchy of models with different levels of
refinement and fidelity, the proposed approach allows the virtual representation to adapt and evolve in tandem with
40 the physical system.

42 Within this context, a number of hybrid methodologies have been proposed to develop representations that adapt
to changes in the system's dynamics. For instance, several studies [32, 33, 34, 35] employ physics-based indicators
to trigger model retraining or refinement steps, often supported by data-driven enrichment of the projection basis
44 for problems such as fracture dynamics. Other approaches, such as [36], introduce basis enrichment through de-
composition, splitting selected reduced-basis vectors into disjoint components and employing vector-space sieving or
46 refinement tree techniques to adapt the reduced-order space. Extensions of these ideas address online model updates,
either through basis compression [37] or additive low-rank updates of reduced spaces [38]. Finally, active learning
48 strategies [39, 40] and probabilistic schemes based on Gaussian Processes and Bayesian networks [41, 42, 43, 44, 45]
have been proposed to assimilate sensor data and build adaptive, data-driven surrogates capable of refining their pre-
50 dictions as new information becomes available.

52 However, existing approaches only partially address the challenge of creating dynamically evolving digital assets,
as model retraining or refinement is typically triggered by response-based error indicators. Such schemes neglect the
overall utility of the virtual representation and cannot explicitly assess the Value of Information (VoI)—that is, the
54 benefit gained from knowledge that improves decision-making [46, 47]. In contrast, this work introduces a Bayesian
decision-theoretic framework that quantifies the expected fidelity and utility of available virtual models when used
56 for generalization or extrapolation. The proposed approach tackles a key challenge in the virtualization process: the
recursive selection of the lowest-cost model capable of achieving the required predictive accuracy for a given engi-
58 neering context [4]. In doing so, it establishes a pathway toward fit-for-purpose digital representations that maximize
decision value and reliability throughout the asset's life-cycle [48].

60 In this context, selecting the optimal model resolution for predicting the response of engineered systems from
a pool of candidate models represents a persistent and critical challenge [49, 50, 51]. These candidate models—or
62 virtual representations—can range from simplified analytical formulations to high-fidelity finite element models, each
offering a different trade-off between accuracy, computational cost, and uncertainty [23]. Effective model selection
64 enables reliable and efficient decision-making for system design and operation by exploiting available monitoring data
to continuously reduce uncertainty [52]. Through Bayesian model updating (BMU) and the recursive assimilation
66 of new information [53, 54], one can estimate the posterior uncertainty associated with each candidate model or
resolution, thereby supporting data-informed and transparent decisions. Consequently, the model selection problem
68 can be naturally formulated as a task of decision-making under uncertainty [55]. The ultimate goal is to identify the
fit-for-purpose model that offers the best balance between accuracy in recovering quantities of interest (QoIs) and
70 computational efficiency. To achieve this, the proposed framework approaches the model selection task through the

lens of Bayesian decision theory, enabling rational and adaptive choices among competing virtual representations [56].

The proposed framework begins by deriving hybrid model representations of varying fidelity levels. Leveraging the extrapolation and generalization capabilities of Reduced-Order Models (ROMs) [57], these are formulated alongside a Full-Order Model (FOM) following [58, 59], with a generic parametrization that accounts for environmental variability, operational changes, and evolving phenomena such as damage or deterioration. The ROMs are then embedded in a sequential Bayesian inference framework that quantifies the posterior uncertainty of each model resolution and guides the selection of the most suitable representation [60]. By recursively assimilating monitoring data, the framework adaptively tracks the evolving state of the physical asset and selects the model that maximizes expected utility, balancing prediction accuracy and computational efficiency for real-time applications. As illustrated in Figure 1, the method autonomously decides whether to retain the current model, switch to another, or trigger retraining—thus enabling adaptive, uncertainty-aware digital twins tailored to the decision context.

Figure 1: Graphical abstract of the proposed adaptive digital-twin framework. Reduced-order and full-order models of varying fidelity are integrated within a Bayesian decision-theoretic scheme that recursively assimilates monitoring data, updates parameters, and selects the model that maximizes expected utility, ensuring an adaptive and efficient representation of the physical asset.

This paper is organized as follows: In section 2, the reduced-order modeling methodology employed to derive the pretrained model resolutions in Figure 1 is presented in short. Section 3 outlines a Bayesian decision-theoretic approach to model selection. In section 4, we describe the numerical case studies used for validation, and the numerical results that highlight the efficiency and effectiveness of the proposed framework. Lastly, section 5 concludes the paper by summarizing our contributions, offering insights, and suggesting directions for future research.

2. Parametric Reduced Order Models

The first component of the proposed framework involves developing parametric reduced-order models (ROMs) through physics-based reduction, yielding low-dimensional surrogates of the full-order model (FOM). These ROMs, illustrated in Figure 1, balance computational speed with predictive accuracy under varying conditions, making them well-suited for downstream tasks in Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) and Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) [61]. The following subsections outline the problem formulation via the governing nonlinear equations of motion and describe the employed ROM methodology.

94 *2.1. Problem Statement*

96 We assume availability of a Full Order Model (FOM), which corresponds to a Finite Element (FE) model that
 97 is suitable for nonlinear structural dynamics simulations. The corresponding dynamical system is dependent on the
 98 input vector $\mathbf{p} = [p_1, \dots, p_k]^T \in \Omega \subset \mathbf{R}^k$, which captures all system- and excitation-relevant parameters. Thus, the
 response is described by the following set of governing equations:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{u}(t), \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t), \mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{F}(t, \mathbf{p}), \quad (1)$$

100 where $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbf{R}^n$ denotes the response in terms of displacements, $\mathbf{M} \in \mathbf{R}^{n \times n}$ the mass matrix, and $\mathbf{F}(t, \mathbf{p}) \in \mathbf{R}^n$ the
 induced excitation. For simplicity, the parametric dependence of the mass matrix is omitted. Nonlinear behavior
 102 is captured through the restoring force term $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{u}(t), \dot{\mathbf{u}}(t), \mathbf{p}) \in \mathbf{R}^n$, which may represent effects such as plasticity,
 hysteresis, or interface nonlinearities, depending on the system response and parameter vector \mathbf{p} . The finite element
 104 (FE) model serving as the full-order model (FOM) is a discretized form of Equation (1). Its full-order dimension n
 defines the size of the coordinate space—and thus the total number of degrees of freedom—governing the model's
 computational cost, as numerical operations scale with n .

106 *2.2. Projection-based model order reduction*

108 The reduction approach employed herein begins with a Galerkin projection scheme, with more general exten-
 sions such as the Petrov–Galerkin method discussed in [62, 63]. As outlined in section 1, a physics-based reduc-
 tion is adopted to enhance interpretability and applicability within higher-level Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)
 110 frameworks. This approach assumes that the system's dynamics—i.e., the solution of Equation (1)—reside in a low-
 dimensional subspace of rank $r \ll n$, where n is the full-order dimension. Accordingly, the system response can be
 112 expressed as:

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{p}) \approx \mathbf{V}(\mathbf{p}) \mathbf{q} \quad (2)$$

114 where $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ represents the projection basis that expresses the aforementioned subspace of the Reduced Order
 Model (ROM) and $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is the low-order coordinate vector. Via substitution of \mathbf{u} into Equation (1) and after
 multiplying the governing set with \mathbf{u}^T , thus performing a Galerkin projection, the following can be derived:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{M}}\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \tilde{\mathbf{g}}(\dot{\mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{p}) = \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(\mathbf{p}, t) \quad (3)$$

116 where $\tilde{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{V}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{g}} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{g}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{F}$. Several techniques exist for constructing the projection basis \mathbf{V} [8]. In
 this work, the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) is employed, using a set of FOM simulations over a training
 118 parameter space to assemble the solution snapshots as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}} = \left[\hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_1) \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_2) \quad \dots \quad \hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_{N_s}) \right] \quad (4)$$

120 where $\hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_i) \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N_t}$ contains the displacement time history for a given parametric realization \mathbf{p}_i , henceforth termed
 as a snapshot, and, as a result, $\hat{\mathbf{S}} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times (N_t \times N_s)}$ is termed the snapshot matrix. The variable N_t represents the number
 of simulation (time) steps and N_s is the total number of snapshots. Via Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$ the
 122 ROM projection basis can be assembled as follows

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{Z}^T \quad (5)$$

and after truncating $\mathbf{\Lambda}$:

$$\mathbf{V} = \left[\mathbf{\Lambda}_1 \quad \mathbf{\Lambda}_2 \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{\Lambda}_r \right] \quad (6)$$

124 where $\mathbf{\Lambda}_i$ is the i column of matrix $\mathbf{\Lambda}$, loosely defined as a Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) mode. Since the
 low-order dimension of Equation (2) is defined as r , the above truncation is applied to obtain the first r orthonormal
 126 components of \mathbf{V} . To define r , a suitable error measure is employed based on the singular value decay [64, 65].

2.3. VpROM: A conditional Variational Autoencoder (cVAE)-boosted ROM

The dynamic behavior of the system, governed by the equations in Equation (1), is highly dependent on the parameter vector \mathbf{p} . As a result, attempting a projection-based reduction with a single basis, as described in Equation (2), might necessitate a large number of modes, resulting in a prohibitively large dimension r and a ROM that proves inefficient or impractical. To handle parametric variability and enable response inference across different operating conditions, a common strategy is to construct a set of local projection bases \mathbf{V}_i , each derived from FOM snapshots $\hat{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{p}_i)$ corresponding to a specific parameter realization \mathbf{p}_i . Subsequent interpolation [66] or clustering [65] methods can then approximate system responses at unseen parameter values [67]. Building upon prior work by the authors [68, 58, 59], the proposed framework employs a conditional Variational Autoencoder (cVAE) as a nonlinear generative model to learn a smooth, generalizable mapping between parameters and basis representations. The resulting VpROM not only accelerates response prediction but also quantifies confidence in its estimates, enhancing its value for SHM applications. Further details on the framework's components can be found in [69] and related references.

To address parametric variability at the ROM level, the two-stage process introduced in [59] is used. First, a collection of local bases is obtained as described and the following system is solved in the least-squares sense:

$$\mathbf{V}_i(\mathbf{p}_i) = \mathbf{V}_{global} * \mathbf{X}_i(\mathbf{p}_i) \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{V}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ is an instance of the collection of local bases, $\mathbf{V}_{global} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times \tilde{r}}$ captures the dynamics across the entire domain and $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{\tilde{r} \times r}$ is a coefficient matrix. \tilde{r} signifies the total number of truncated modes retained on \mathbf{V}_{global} and can be computed similarly to r . Second, interpolation is performed on the coefficient matrices \mathbf{X}_i . These comprise a reduced size ($\tilde{r} \ll r$), thus removing any dependency on the FOM dimension n offering additional efficiency. After interpolating the coefficient matrices \mathbf{X}_i , the corresponding local ROM basis \mathbf{V} can be obtained for any validation parametric sample. In [59] the local bases \mathbf{V} are projected first to the tangent space of the proper Grassmannian manifold, where the interpolation operations performed will output a local basis that retains key properties like orthogonality [70, 71]. Alternatively, a re-orthogonalization step can be performed after interpolating the coefficient matrices and recovering the projection basis.

This work builds upon the framework introduced in [58], which employs a conditional Variational Autoencoder (cVAE) as a generative model capable of recursively inferring the local basis from features extracted from monitoring data. The cVAE acts as a nonlinear generator and approximator of the coefficient matrices \mathbf{X} , and consequently of the local projection subspaces \mathbf{V} and associated ROMs. Parametric variability is incorporated directly at the ROM level by conditioning the cVAE on known system parameters or on features derived from measured responses. In previous formulations [69, 58], the VpROM was designed in a generalized manner, assuming no prior knowledge of the true parameter vector \mathbf{p} during training or deployment; instead, the cVAE infers the local basis from observed response features. When the parameters \mathbf{p} are known, they can directly serve as conditioning inputs. Finally, the probabilistic nature of the cVAE allows the VpROM to quantify prediction uncertainty: the latent space defines a learned probability distribution whose sampling enables propagation of uncertainty through the ROM, yielding confidence bounds and error estimates on the predicted responses.

The overall framework is illustrated in Figure 2. The conditioning features \mathbf{W} are concatenated with the input \mathbf{X} and the latent variables \mathbf{Z} . Formally, the encoder learns the conditional distribution $q_\theta(\mathbf{Z}|\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{W})$, while the decoder reconstructs the data via $p_\phi(\mathbf{X}|\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{W})$. For simplicity, we set $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{p}$, since parameter inference is handled separately within the Bayesian inference framework shown in Figure 1. Accordingly, the system variability in Equation (1) is represented by \mathbf{p} , and the mapping from \mathbf{p} to the local bases \mathbf{V} in Equation (3) is learned through the relationship between \mathbf{p} and the reduced coefficient matrices \mathbf{X} in Equation (7).

Once trained, the conditional VAE serves as a generative model capable of sampling the reduced basis coefficients \mathbf{X}_i defined in Equation (7). Given an inferred parameter realization $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ from Bayesian inference, samples drawn from the latent distribution are decoded to generate the corresponding \mathbf{X} values. In this work, a diagonal Gaussian prior is adopted for the latent space, as depicted in Figure 3.

2.4. Uncertainty Bounds via the Unscented Transform

Once the decoder is trained, predictions are obtained by sampling the inferred variational distribution of the latent space and decoding these samples. A realization of the random variable ϵ is first drawn and transformed into \mathbf{Z}

Figure 2: The architecture of the employed cVAE. The conditioning features W are injected via concatenation with the input vector X and the latent space Z .

Figure 3: Architecture of the cVAE in basis generation mode: The prior distribution ϵ is sampled, and the latent vectors are taken after concatenating with the (inferred) vector \hat{p} . Dimensionality serves only illustrative purposes.

using the deterministic mean μ_θ and standard deviation σ_θ inferred by the encoder. The latent vector Z is then concatenated with the inferred parameters \hat{p} and passed through the decoder to generate samples from $p_\phi(\hat{X}|Z, \hat{p})$ —each representing a possible realization of the reduced coefficients X . By repeating this process, the mean and variance of the estimated coefficients and projection bases can be evaluated. Subsequent parallel ROM simulations using these sampled bases, as defined in Equation (3), enable uncertainty propagation from the latent space to the output response. The resulting ensemble statistics yield numerical error bounds that quantify prediction uncertainty, as demonstrated in [68, 58].

The sampling procedure described above can be computationally expensive, as hundreds of samples may be required to capture the system's response uncertainty [58]. To improve efficiency, we adopt the Unscented Transform (UT) [72, 73], which exploits the Gaussian nature of the latent distributions to generate a deterministic set of sigma points instead of numerous random samples. These sigma points are propagated through the decoder, and the resulting outputs are combined using predefined weights that preserve the mean and covariance of the original Gaussian distribution, yielding accurate and efficient uncertainty estimates.

2.5. Hyper-reduction

Hyper-reduction provides a second-level approximation that alleviates the computational cost of updating and reconstructing the nonlinear term \tilde{g} in Equation (3) [74]. Here, we employ the Energy Conserving Mesh Sampling and Weighting (ECSW) method [75], a well-established physics-based technique. Comprehensive discussions of ECSW

192 and related approaches can be found in [76, 77, 78]. In brief, ECSW selects a subset of finite elements from the
 194 FE discretization—used here as the FOM—by solving a nonlinear optimization problem that ensures the weighted
 196 projections of the nonlinear terms accurately approximate the total internal work. Once the optimal subset and corresponding weights are determined, a Hyper-ROM is obtained, as depicted in Figure 1, offering a substantial reduction in computational cost. Among the available model resolutions, the Hyper-ROM achieves the highest efficiency, the FOM the highest fidelity, and standard ROMs occupy the intermediate range.

198 3. A Bayesian decision-theoretic approach to model selection

The framework outlined in the previous section can be employed to generate different model resolutions to assist
 200 with decision-making and SHM tasks. Specifically, we have highlighted three resolutions in Figure 1, each one
 202 corresponding to a trade-off between computational efficiency and fidelity: a) The full-order FE model of the system,
 204 termed FOM, which offers the highest possible precision, b) the ROM that strike a balance between precision and
 206 efficiency, and c) the Hyper ROM, which corresponds to the developed ROM equipped with hyper-reduction, and
 potentially offers the highest efficiency. Furthermore, the proposed framework allows for the development of virtual
 models conditioned on system dependencies, thus capturing parametric variability.

As physical infrastructure assets evolve over time, a recursive challenge emerges: determining which parametric
 208 instance and model resolution provide the best balance between computational cost and predictive accuracy. This
 210 model selection task, conditioned on incoming response data, can be naturally formulated as a decision-making under
 212 uncertainty (DMUU) problem, where the optimal choice is the model that maximizes the expected utility [79, 80].
 In decision theory, utility serves as a formal measure to evaluate the relative desirability of alternative actions. It
 is defined through an objective function that maps the attributes of a decision to a numerical value representing its
 overall benefit. In the present context, two primary attributes govern the utility of a model:

- 214 1. Model fidelity, in terms of recovering target Quantities of Interest (QoIs), and
2. Model cost, in terms of computational complexity and runtime.

These attributes are central to the problem, as virtual models used in decision-making and SHM applications
 216 inherently balance precision against computational cost. They are also competing by nature: higher precision typically
 218 entails higher cost. Bayesian decision theory [56, 79] offers a rigorous framework for solving decision-making
 under uncertainty (DMUU) problems, where information becomes available recursively and progressively reduces
 uncertainty in decision-making.

Let θ denote the random vector of uncertain model parameters. For simplicity, we assume these coincide with
 220 the modeling parameters of the FOM and ROMs in Eqs. 1, 3, and Figure 3, i.e., $\theta = \hat{\mathbf{p}}$. This assumption is not
 222 restrictive—the framework remains valid provided $\theta \subseteq \mathbf{p}$. Hence, the model parametrization introduced in section 2
 is kept intentionally general, as the parameter vector directly governs model selection. In turn, a prior probabilistic
 224 model $\pi_{\text{pr}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$ needs to be assigned. The incoming recorded signals, collectively denoted as monitoring data \mathbf{d} , can
 be leveraged to perform inference and Bayesian model updating (BMU), which outputs the posterior distribution of
 226 $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ given \mathbf{d} , denoted by $\pi_{\text{pos}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{d})$. The optimal model to be selected M_{opt} conditional on the monitoring data \mathbf{d} can
 then be obtained as:

$$M_{\text{opt}|\mathbf{d}} = \underset{\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n\}}{\text{argmax}} \mathbb{E}_{\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{d}, M_i} [U_i], \quad (8)$$

where $U_i = U(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i)$

228 where U is the considered utility function that relates the uncertain parameter vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ and models M , thus mapping
 possible outcomes to their utility as illustrated in Figure 4. The expectation \mathbb{E} in Equation (8) is evaluated with respect
 230 to the posterior distribution $\pi_{\text{pos}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{y}, M_i)$. The possible decisions are summarized in the set $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_k\}$ in the
 case of k competing models, where M_i represents the decision to employ the i -th model for inferring the parameter
 232 and recovering the dynamic behavior of the engineered system of interest.

As discussed, two competing attributes define the utility function U in this work: model fidelity and computational
 234 efficiency. Illustrative examples of the resulting utility branches are shown in Figure 4. In Figure 4a the considered
 utility curve with respect to the ability of the model to recover the quantity of interest is depicted, also accounting for

(a) Utility U_f as a function of the model fidelity.

(b) Utility U_e as a function of the model runtime.

Figure 4: Example utility functions for the considered competing attributes, namely i) model fidelity, which accounts for over/under-estimating target quantities, and (ii) computational runtime to ensure real-time inference when possible.

236 over- and under-estimation effects. Underestimation of quantities of interest is here penalized more as it might lead
 238 to unexpected failures and catastrophic events, which are considered more critical in asset management compared to
 240 potential additional costs caused by overestimation. Since the Bayesian inference framework is also employed for pa-
 242 rameter estimation, the utility with respect to the model's precision is evaluated using readings from redundant sensor
 measurements that are not employed on the inference of $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$. In Figure 4b the implemented relationship between the
 evaluation time of the model and its utility is reported. The overall utility can be computed as a weighted combination
 of the competing attributes, allowing the decision-maker to weigh the considered attributes according to the decision
 at hand. The corresponding mathematical formulation reads:

$$U_i(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = \gamma * U_i(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) + (1 - \gamma) * U_i(\text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) \quad (9)$$

$$U_i(\text{fidelity}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = U_f(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = \begin{cases} 1 - w_1 * \left(\frac{y_f - \hat{y}_f}{y_f}\right)^2 * (w_1 * \epsilon_{max})^{-1}, & (y_f - \hat{y}_f) > 0 \\ 1 - w_2 * \left(\frac{y_f - \hat{y}_f}{y_f}\right)^2 * (w_2 * \epsilon_{max})^{-1}, & (y_f - \hat{y}_f) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$U_i(\text{efficiency}|M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = U_e(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i) = 1 - \frac{\log^2(t_{M_i})}{\log^2(t_{max})} \quad (11)$$

244 where y_f denotes the observed values for the QoI and \hat{y} the model-approximated ones using the inferred $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ and the se-
 246 lected model resolution M_i . The variable t_{M_i} denotes the evaluation time of model resolution M_i , t_{max} is the maximum
 248 acceptable evaluation time that corresponds to zero utility and ϵ_{max} the maximum prediction error that is penalized
 with zero utility. The weights w_1, w_2 are chosen properly to account for over- and under-estimation effects ($w_1 > w_2$)
 and to normalize the computed discrepancy so that the maximum possible utility is equal to 1, as illustrated in Fig-
 250 ure 4, where $w_1 = 3, w_2 = 1, t_{max} = 10s, \epsilon_{max} = 20\%$. The factor γ weighs the importance of fidelity in the task at
 hand, also reflecting a balancing act with the corresponding efficiency.

For the Bayesian model updating (BMU) task, the improved Transitional Markov Chain Monte Carlo (iTMC) method is employed [49, 81], adapted from the open-source implementation available at <https://github.com/ERA-Software/Overview>. An initial ensemble of $n_s = 1000$ samples is drawn from the prior distribution $\pi_{pr}(\hat{\mathbf{p}})$. The updating step is then performed conditionally on the observed data \mathbf{y} to obtain the posterior distribution of the uncertain parameters, $\pi_{pos}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{y})$. The discrepancy between the measured acceleration signals \mathbf{y} and the model-predicted

256 responses $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$ is modeled probabilistically as:

$$nRMS E(\hat{\mathbf{p}}, M_i) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_f} (\mathbf{y}_j - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_j(\hat{\mathbf{p}}, M_i))^2}{\sum_{j=1}^{n_f} \mathbf{y}_j^2}} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_f} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Sigma} = \text{diag}(c^2 \|\mathbf{y}\|^2)) \quad (12)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Sigma})$ denotes the multivariate normal (MVN) distribution with a zero-mean vector and covariance matrix $\mathbf{\Sigma}$.
 258 A diagonal covariance matrix is assumed, with the variance of each component assumed proportional to the L_2 -norm
 of \mathbf{y} . The factor c can be regarded as a coefficient of variation, and its chosen value reflects the total prediction error.
 260 It is here assumed that $c = 0.10$. The likelihood function can be then written as:

$$L(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{y}) \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\eta}; \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Sigma}), \quad (13)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(\cdot; \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Sigma})$ denotes the value of the MVN density function at a specified location. Thus, the expected fidelity
 262 utility U_f to employ model M_i can be approximated using n_s posterior samples from $\pi_{\text{pos}}(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{y})$ as:

$$\mathbb{E}_{\hat{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{y}, M_i}[U_f(\hat{\mathbf{p}}|M_i)] \approx \frac{1}{n_s} \sum_{j=1}^{n_s} U_f(M_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_j), \quad (14)$$

The equivalent is implemented for U_e .

264 4. Numerical case studies

The proposed framework is validated in two structural dynamics case studies, involving hysteretic, geometric,
 266 and material nonlinearities. In both cases, the approach performs recursive model selection to identify the optimal
 resolution for structural assets whose state, parameters, and health condition evolve over time. The considered model
 268 resolutions are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Reference table for the considered model resolutions.

Reference name	Description
FOM	The full-order FE model
$VpROM$	ROM according to the formulation in subsection 2.3.
$H-VpROM$	$VpROM$ additionally equipped with hyper-reduction
Perturbed FOM	The full-order FE model with a finer mesh and perturbed material properties. Used for generating response signals with a 8% noise level for testing.

Given the limited availability of experimental or field monitoring data, simulated measurements are used for
 270 validation. These are generated from an independent numerical finite element (FE) model, referred to as the perturbed
 FOM, as summarized in Table 1. To clearly distinguish the monitoring data used for testing from the FOM employed
 272 in constructing the ROMs, the following measures are adopted:

- The perturbed FOM employs a finer finite element mesh than the in-house FOM used to train the ROMs.
- The Young's modulus E is randomly perturbed, with element-wise values drawn from a normal distribution
 274 with mean E_{ref} and standard deviation 5, GPa.
- Measurement noise corresponding to 8% of the root-mean-square (RMS) value of each signal is added.
 276

The perturbed FOM is employed to generate the testing data in order to avoid the inverse crime [82, 83], which
 278 arises when the same or nearly identical model is used both to generate and to infer system responses in an inverse
 problem [84].

280 The performance of the proposed framework in parameter and response inference (see Figure 1) is assessed by
 reproducing the time-history response of selected quantities of interest or their spatial distribution at specific simula-
 282 tion snapshots. Parameter inference is based on vibration measurements from accelerometers assumed to be installed

on the perturbed FOM of the structure. For the model selection task, the utility is evaluated using data from redundant sensors not involved in the inference process, potentially including other quantities of interest such as stresses or displacements. The specific monitoring and inference configurations are detailed separately for each case study.

All FOM and ROM numerical simulations, including model training, are performed using an in-house finite element (FE) code on a workstation equipped with an 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 processor (2.80 GHz) and 32 GB RAM. The FE solver employs Newmark integration for time-history analysis, with both the FOM and ROM sharing the same mesh and time-step size. This is done to enable a fair comparison when reporting computational speed-ups, however, further efficiency can be achieved by increasing the time-step of the ROM without losing accuracy [77]. The Bayesian inference and model updating tasks are carried out in Euler, a high-performance cluster available to all ETH groups. This is done to enable multiple model evaluations in parallel during the iTMCMC steps. Reported speed-up factors refer solely to the online evaluation phase, are averaged over all model evaluations during the iTMCMC steps and exclude the offline training cost of the ROM. The speed-up is computed as $t_{\text{FOM}}/t_{\text{ROM}}$, where t denotes the model evaluation time for approximating the QoIs in the given monitoring window.

4.1. Benchmark Shear Frame with Hysteretic Links

As an initial example, we consider an open-source, benchmark multi-degree of freedom nonlinear response simulator of a three-dimensional shear frame with nodal couplings that exhibit Bouc-Wen hysteresis, available in [85]. Specifically, the following case study that requires decision-making under an adaptive model deployment is defined: A shear frame representing a structural asset, like a hospital building, experiences ground motion excitation reflecting an earthquake scenario. The structure behaves linearly at first, but its column joints get damaged in an uneven manner due to the ground motion. At the same time, we assume a SHM-related decision has to be made in real-time relying on model-based response inference. The proposed framework is utilized to recursively identify the optimal model that maximizes the cost-to-efficiency tradeoff, defined as the utility, to be used for response inference at any given time. This setup is summarized in Table 2. This demonstrative example is chosen due to the relevance of the simulator to real-life infrastructure assets and its inherent ability to parametrically model multiple simultaneously activated instances of nonlinearity, representing damage or condition deterioration in different regions.

Table 2: Details of the monitoring setup for the shear frame case study.

Scenario	Frame behaves linearly at first. Structure and column joints get damaged (unevenly) due to ground motion.
Objective	Select model to be used for SHM-related downstream tasks
Monitoring Data	Nodal accelerations
QoIs for Utility computation	Four nodes monitored (blue crosses in Fig. 5a) Fidelity: Inter-story drift (Normalized RMSE) Efficiency: Avg. model evaluation time (s)
Utility functions	Equations 9-11, Figure 4, $t_{\text{max}} = 10\text{s}$, $w_1 = 3$, $w_2 = 1$, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 20\%$
Monitoring window	1 second rolling windows

A schematic of the shear frame setup is shown in Figure 5a, where the colored columns indicate regions subject to progressive damage. Damage is introduced with varying intensity and timing, as defined through the parametric formulation. All joints in Figure 5a are modeled using the Bouc-Wen hysteretic formulation, a smooth nonlinear model widely used to represent material hysteresis [86]. Following the benchmark in [85], a Bouc-Wen model is implemented at each degree of freedom (DOF) of every nodal link to simulate the total restoring force \mathbf{R} . An illustration of the nonlinear mechanism along the longitudinal x -DOF is provided in Figure 5b. In this formulation, \mathbf{R} is expressed as the superposition of linear and nonlinear terms, represented by the two springs in Figure 5b, and depends on the instantaneous nodal displacement δu and its hysteretic component z . The vectorized governing equations for all DOFs of a link are given as:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_{\text{linear}} + \mathbf{R}_{\text{hysteretic}} = \alpha k \mathbf{d} \mathbf{u} + (1 - \alpha) k \mathbf{z} \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{du} represents the nodal displacement, α denotes the characteristic post-yield to elastic stiffness ratio, and k is the corresponding stiffness coefficient of the link. The variable \mathbf{z} represents the hysteretic portion of the elongation, or displacement in general, and controls the hysteretic forcing. It obeys the following

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \frac{A\mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}} - \nu(t)(\beta|\mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}}|\mathbf{z}|^w - \gamma\mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}}|\mathbf{z}|^w)}{\eta(t)} \quad (16)$$

$$\nu(t) = 1.0 + \delta_\nu \epsilon(t), \quad \eta(t) = 1.0 + \delta_\eta \epsilon(t), \quad \epsilon(t) = \int_0^t \mathbf{z} \mathbf{d}\dot{\mathbf{u}} dt \quad (17)$$

where the shape, smoothness, and amplitude of the hysteretic curve that characterizes the dynamic behavior of each joint are determined by parameters β , γ , w , and A . Their absolute values are not of interest, but rather their sums or differences, which may indicate a hardening or softening relationship [87, 88]. The terms $\nu(t)$ and $\eta(t)$ are introduced to capture strength deterioration and stiffness degradation effects via the corresponding coefficients δ_ν and δ_η . In turn, their evolution in time depends on the absorbed hysteretic energy $\epsilon(t)$.

Figure 5: Schematic of the shear frame and link mechanism. Colored columns mark regions where damage is introduced. Blue crosses denote sensor locations, and the black cross indicates a redundant sensor.

Thus, the employed benchmark allows for a structural dynamics simulator, which is parameterized with respect to system properties and the traits of each joints' behavior. In turn, damage and deterioration case studies can be accordingly defined. As illustrated in Figure 5a by the colored columns, we assume damage happens in the basement or second floor columns via modifying the k parameter of Equation (15) in the corresponding links. We also consider the Young modulus E as a varying parameter, to address global damage scenarios. Thus, the parameter vector to be inferred in Equation (8) is $\mathbf{p} = [E, \alpha, k_1, k_2, k_3]$, where E is the Young modulus of the frame, and k_i indicates the k parameter in the links of floor i . As mentioned, α is a characteristic parameter representing the post-yield to elastic stiffness ratio and permanent damage in a system typically changes k_i [87]. However, changing α along k_i is a conscious choice here to elevate the difficulty and simulate a frame that behaves linearly at first and experiences damage modeled via the nonlinear springs. (setting $\alpha = 0.1$). For every scenario, after damage and setting $\alpha = 0.1$ no further changes in α occur. The range and distribution of the parameters employed for the FOM and for deriving the VpROMs are summarized in Table 3. Parameter k_3 is not varied on purpose during derivation of the considered ROMs to be used later for simulating an unseen damage event. Regarding material properties, steel HEA cross sections are used for all beam elements, and the structure is assembled using two frames along the x -axis, each of length $l = 7.5$ m length and width $w = 5$ m. All stories have a height of $h = 3.2$ m.

The frame is subjected to base excitation representing seismic loading. Base accelerograms are applied at an angle of $\theta = \pi/4$ relative to the longitudinal axis. During training, synthetic accelerograms generated from white-noise inputs are used in combination with Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) of 500 parameter realizations of \mathbf{p} . For

Table 3: System properties and range of parameter values for the training of the ROMs. Variable α changes during operation to signify the initiation of damage.

Parameter:	E ($\times 210$ GPa)	k_1, k_2 ($\times 1e^8$)	α	β	γ	δ_η, δ_v	A, w
Range:	[0.70, 1.0]	[0.6, 1.0]	$\in \{0.1, 1\}$	3.0	4.0	0.0	1.0

testing, 250 samples are employed, with excitations formed as weighted combinations of the Kobe and Northridge earthquakes [89].

The employed monitoring scheme summarized in Table 2 uses four acceleration sensors at different nodes indicated via blue crosses in Figure 5a. Each sensor records acceleration in both the longitudinal and vertical directions, and these data are used for the parameter inference task described in Figure 1. The top-story inter-story drift is also assumed to be monitored and serves as a reference metric to quantify model precision within the model selection framework. This choice is motivated by the strong correlation between inter-story drift and the structural integrity and seismic resilience of frame systems, making it a key indicator for both design and condition monitoring [90, 91]. Alternatively, data from a redundant vibration sensor could be used for this purpose [92].

Figure 6: Example input ground motion accelerogram with condition deterioration events indicated by red lines. Initially the frame is assumed undamaged, and thus $\mathbf{p} = [1.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0]$.

An example testing scenario is described herein. The testing ground motion accelerogram is depicted in Figure 6. This is assumed to be known and is considered as input to the proposed framework, along with windows of monitoring data from the deployed acceleration sensors, as illustrated in Figure 1. The testing scenario includes three condition deterioration events, illustrated with red dashed lines in Figure 6. Specifically, the frame is initially assumed healthy ($\alpha = 1.0$). During the first damage event, we set $\alpha = 0.10$ and change the corresponding stiffness coefficients ($k_1 = 0.84, k_2 = 1.0, k_3 = 0.92$). Although changing α during the simulation is not a realistic assumption, this is a deliberate choice here to elevate the difficulty and cause abrupt damage via the nonlinear springs. This happens only during the first damage event, α remains the same afterward. In the second event, the stiffness coefficients of the hysteretic springs in the first and last floor reduce unevenly, reflecting localized damage while the E modulus also reduces. Lastly, the third event reduces all three stiffness coefficients k_1, k_2, k_3 to values outside the operational regime of Table 3 that was considered for deriving the parametric ROMs. This extreme case is designed to challenge the accuracy of the available reduced representations and test whether the framework will signal that only the FOM is suitable for any decision-making or SHM task, thus also triggering a retraining step for the derived ROMs.

The utility readings for the example scenario in Figure 6 are shown in Figure 7, with each competing attribute reported separately. The plots present raw utility values without smoothing or window averaging, while damage events are indicated by black dotted lines at their respective timestamps. In Figure 7a, the fidelity-related utility

Figure 7: Evaluations of the fidelity and efficiency utility functions for the considered model resolutions. Dashed lines indicate damage events and the dotted line a potential threshold to signal model retraining.

368 corresponding to the recovery of inter-story drift is evaluated following Figure 4a and Equation (10). As expected,
 370 all model resolutions achieve high accuracy in reproducing the target quantity before the 40s mark, aside from mi-
 372 nor low-amplitude oscillations. These fluctuations arise from the inherent latency of the ROMs in capturing abrupt
 374 dynamic changes—as present in the test scenario—and from stochastic variations in the response. The consistently
 376 high utility values before 40s confirm the robustness and reliability of the (hyper-)reduced-order models in delivering
 378 accurate predictions under parametric variability. However, following the damage event at 40s, only the FOM main-
 tains sufficient accuracy for decision-making, as the parameter k_3 (excluded from the ROM training) varies and the
 parameters k_1, k_2 exceed the original training domain. While physics-based ROMs are known to exhibit good extrap-
 olation capabilities, such a loss in accuracy under extreme, out-of-distribution events is expected. Consequently, the
 proposed framework correctly identifies that the FOM should be selected when high-fidelity predictions are required.
 Moreover, by defining an appropriate threshold—as illustrated in Figures 7a and 8—the total or fidelity utility U_f can
 serve as a triggering indicator for adapting or retraining the model representation.

Figure 8: Total utility evaluations for different weighted combinations of the considered attributes in Equation (9). Dashed lines indicate damage events and the dotted line a potential threshold to signal model retraining.

380 Following Equation (9), the total utility is recursively evaluated and reported in Figure 8. The framework effec-
 tively tracks system state changes by recursively inferring the corresponding parametric traits, updating the underlying

382 model representations, and identifying the optimal model for downstream tasks. As the optimal selection results from
 384 maximizing the utility function, it inherently reflects the trade-off between fidelity and efficiency. In Figure 8a, where
 both attributes are equally weighted, the framework identifies the H-VpROM and the FOM as the most suitable models
 before and after the 40s event, respectively. For demonstration purposes, Figure 8b illustrates a case where computa-
 386 tional efficiency is prioritized ($\gamma = 0.3$ in Equation (9)), leading the framework to select the VpROM as the preferred
 model following the 40s extreme event.

Figure 9: Bayesian parameter inference for obtaining the posterior distribution of the uncertain model parameters after the second damage event in Figure 6.

388 To further evaluate the framework's performance, two representative examples of the Bayesian parameter infer-
 ence task are shown in Figure 9. For each case, the prior and posterior distributions of the uncertain parameters
 390 are reported following the second damage event depicted in Figure 6. Results are presented at two discrete time
 instances—1,s and 2,s after the event—and for all considered model resolutions: the FOM, the VpROM, and its
 392 hyper-reduced variant. A slight to pronounced bimodality can be observed in the distributions in Figure 9a–Figure 9b,
 including the prior, which is attributed to the relatively small sample size n_s . To preserve computational efficiency,
 394 this number was intentionally kept limited.

As shown in Figure 9, the accuracy of parameter inference depends on both the forward model resolution and
 396 the amount of monitoring information available. This underscores the importance of using the utility function as
 the key metric for model selection, as it balances fidelity and efficiency according to the needs of the downstream
 398 task. All model resolutions show limited performance when inference is conducted only 1,s after the damage event
 (Figures 9a–9b). However, once 2,s of additional response data are assimilated, all models converge more closely
 400 to the true parameter values, and the posterior distributions become significantly smoother (Figures 9c–9d). Among

the tested resolutions, the FOM achieves the highest precision, followed by the VpROM and the hyper-reduced H-VpROM, as expected.

(a) Response approximation using H-VpROM.

(b) Response approximation using VpROM.

Figure 10: Framework's response approximation quality and corresponding error bounds. The framework is evaluated at the 30s mark, and the reduced models are used for inference and a 5s-ahead response prediction.

The probabilistic formulation of the proposed framework enables explicit uncertainty quantification of the predicted responses. As illustrated in Figure 9, the parameter inference and BMU process yields posterior distributions that can be sampled at any desired confidence level. This allows the uncertainty in parameter estimates to be propagated to the model predictions by evaluating the response for each sampled realization of the selected model resolution. These evaluations can be executed in parallel, maintaining computational efficiency. An equivalent procedure applies to the ROMs, as detailed in subsection 2.4, where the probabilistic latent space is sampled via the Unscented Transform to generate projection bases and corresponding response error bounds [58]. Consequently, the framework can quantify and propagate uncertainty in the form of confidence or error bounds on the approximated responses. This is demonstrated in Figure 10, where at the 30s mark the VpROM and H-VpROM perform inference and a 5s-ahead prediction. The resulting bounds encapsulate the model response, providing a direct measure of confidence and predictive reliability relevant for downstream decision-making tasks.

For completeness, the average inference and prediction performance of all model resolutions across the full set of testing scenarios is summarized in Table 4. Unlike the illustrative example discussed earlier, the results reported in Table 4 exclude extreme events such as the final excitation shown in Figure 6.

Table 4: Parameter and response approximation error across all testing excitations. The average performance is reported and no extreme events are considered. The RMSE is reported for the monitored acceleration signals.

	$\ E - \hat{E}\ $	$\ k_1 - \hat{k}_1\ $	$\ k_2 - \hat{k}_2\ $	RMSE	$\ \text{Drift} - \hat{\text{Drift}}\ $	Speed-up
FOM	< 1%	1.72%	4.02%	9%	1.56%	1.0
VpROM	4.44%	3.44%	8.53%	12%	2.03%	3.25
H-VpROM	5.32%	4.46%	10.30%	16%	2.90%	10.35

4.2. Simplified fuselage panel

418 The second numerical example concerns a simplified fuselage panel, a representative load-carrying component in
 420 both maritime and aerospace structures, and therefore of broad practical relevance. This example is loosely inspired
 by [93], where dynamic substructuring was applied to analyze cracking in thin-walled aeronautic structures. Here,
 we adopt and extend the implementation proposed in [20] for model assembly, modifying it to account for large
 422 deformations and the resulting geometric nonlinearities.

Figure 11: Simplified fuselage panel geometry, loading, and sensor locations. The blue sensors are used for inference while the red redundant sensor is employed for performance and utility evaluation.

424 The fuselage panel geometry, boundary conditions, loading, and sensor layout are shown in Figure 11. The panel is
 cylindrical with a radius of 2.5 m and a uniform thickness of 3 mm. An aluminum material is assumed, with a variable
 Young's modulus E_p introduced to amplify large deformations and thus capture geometric nonlinearities. Unlike
 426 previous studies employing free-free or fully fixed conditions, the present setup applies fixed boundary conditions
 only along the left edge, while the right edge is connected through springs of variable stiffness k_b to represent bolted
 428 joint loosening. The stiffness parameter ranges from 0 (free end) to 1 (fully fixed). The fuselage is discretized
 using 4,393 MITC4 elements, resulting in 47,334 degrees of freedom. A dynamic pressure load is applied uniformly,
 430 following a white-noise-like signal with parametric magnitude p in the frequency range [1, 250] Hz over a duration
 of 2 s. Time integration is performed using the implicit Newmark scheme with a step size of $\Delta t = 2 \times 10^{-4}$ s.

Table 5: System properties and range of parametric traits.

Parameter:	E_p ($\times 25$ GPa)	k_b ($\times 1e^{16}$)	p (kN/m ²)	Poisson's ratio	Density (kg/m ³)
Range:	[1.0, 2.0]	[0.0, 1.0]	[0.1, 1.0]	$\nu = 0.3$	$\rho = 2700$

432 The system properties and the parametric dependencies of the model are summarized in Table 5. The parameter
 vector to be inferred is $\mathbf{p} = [E_p, k_b, p]$. The material parameter E_p can simulate potential damage on the fuselage and
 434 influence the geometrically nonlinear behavior directly. Similarly, parameter k_b controls the rigidity of the boundary
 and can model fixed-free or fixed-fixed conditions and bolt loosening or equivalent damage events in a simplified
 436 manner. Lastly, the amplitude of the excitation p influences the deformation amplitude, and thus, the nonlinear
 behavior.

438 For training the ROMs listed in Table 1, $r = 32$ basis modes are employed along with 500 training samples of \mathbf{p}
 generated via Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS). Testing is performed using 200 parametric samples. The monitoring
 440 setup, summarized in Table 6, includes eight acceleration sensors placed at distinct nodes (blue dots in Figure 11),
 each recording acceleration along the excitation direction. These measurements are used for the parameter inference
 442 task, as described in Figure 1. A redundant sensor (sensor 9, shown in red in Figure 11) provides independent vibration
 data to trigger adaptive model selection and assess model fidelity. The utility functions follow the same formulation

444 as in Equations 9–11 and Figure 4, except that in the efficiency utility, the maximum penalized evaluation time (zero utility) is set to 100 instead of 10 seconds.

Table 6: Details of the monitoring setup for the fuselage panel.

Scenario	Panel exhibits geometric nonlinearity and parametric material and boundary traits while experiencing 2s excitation windows of varying amplitude.
Objective	Select model to be used for SHM-related downstream tasks
Monitoring Data	Nodal accelerations Eight nodes monitored (blue dots in Fig. 11)
QoIs for Utility computation	Fidelity: Max. acceleration at redundant sensor 9 (Normalized RMSE) Efficiency: Avg. model evaluation time (s)
Utility functions	Equations 9-11, $t_{max} = 100s$, $w_1 = 3$, $w_2 = 1$, $\epsilon_{max} = 25\%$
Monitoring window	0.5 seconds rolling windows

446 As summarized in Table 6, the testing scenarios consist of repeated 2-second windows with evolving parametric
 448 traits. The excitation amplitude p varies freely within each sequence, while the material modulus E_p and boundary
 449 stiffness k_b decrease progressively to emulate structural deterioration. For instance, E_p may decrease from 1.65 to
 450 1.42, 1.12, and so forth. Performance validation includes 50 such combinations, with parameter realizations drawn via
 451 LHS. A representative example of the Bayesian parameter inference results for the excitation amplitude and boundary
 452 stiffness is shown in Figure 12; similar trends are observed for the material parameter E_p . The reported results
 453 correspond to the best-performing 2-second window among the rolling sequences. Despite minor discrepancies, the
 454 proposed framework successfully reconstructs the evolving parametric configuration from the sensing data, enabling
 adaptive model updates in real time.

Figure 12: Bayesian parameter inference for obtaining the posterior distribution of the uncertain model parameters. A representative average performance example is shown.

456 As shown in Figure 12, the FOM exhibits the highest precision in capturing the underlying parameters, as ex-
 457 pected. This trend is confirmed in Figure 13a, where the FOM achieves the greatest fidelity utility U_f . However, this
 458 accuracy comes at a substantial computational cost, as reflected by the very low efficiency utility U_e in Figure 13b.
 459 Conversely, the H-VpROM provides hyper-accelerated evaluations, yielding high U_e values while maintaining accept-
 460 able accuracy. The VpROM demonstrates a similar trend, attaining a different but still favorable accuracy–efficiency
 trade-off. These results highlight the importance of the utility-based formulation, which quantitatively balances com-
 peting attributes and enables data-informed model selection and validation.

462 Following Equation (9), the competing utility attributes can be balanced through an appropriate choice of the
 weighting coefficient γ . This parameter can be defined by the decision maker, allowing task-specific prioritization

Figure 13: Evaluations of the fidelity and efficiency utility functions for the considered model resolutions for a representative example testing scenario. Red dotted lines indicate parameter changes.

464 between fidelity and efficiency. Two illustrative examples of the resulting total utility for different γ values are presented in Figure 14. As shown in Figure 13, the H-VpROM consistently achieves the highest utility under the equal weighting scheme, owing to its superior computational performance, and is thus identified as the optimal model for the given task (see Figure 14a). When precision is prioritized ($\gamma = 0.75$), however, the VpROM becomes more favorable, as shown in Figure 14b. These results emphasize the value of utility-based model selection, which enables context-aware adaptation by quantifying trade-offs between competing objectives.

Figure 14: Total utility evaluations for different weighted combinations of the considered attributes in Figure 13. Red dotted lines indicate parameter changes.

470 Following the model updating and selection process, and based on the posterior distributions in Figure 12, the H-VpROM is employed for response prediction. Owing to its physics-aware formulation, the model can recover quantities of interest across all physical fields. Samples drawn from the posterior distributions are propagated through the H-VpROM to quantify confidence bounds on the predicted responses. By further combining these samples with draws from the model's probabilistic latent space via the Unscented Transform (see subsection 2.4), the resulting bounds also account for uncertainty in the reduced representation itself. The corresponding H-VpROM predictions are shown in Figures 15–16 for the system's displacement and acceleration responses. The reported average and maximum error estimates are computed across all testing configurations, using the highest-utility H-VpROM identified in the

478 initial rolling windows.

Figure 15: Predicted displacement response at the redundant node with associated confidence bounds. Reported values include the average and maximum approximation errors across all testing samples.

As shown in Figure 15a, the framework effectively balances computational efficiency and accuracy, delivering highly consistent response estimates on average. Moreover, the probabilistic formulation and embedded Bayesian components enable the framework to provide confidence bounds that enclose the true response, even under the maximum error scenario depicted in Figure 15b. Similar trends are observed for the acceleration response in Figure 16. As discussed in the previous case study, the decision-maker can define a precision utility threshold U_f to automatically trigger model retraining in real time, avoiding delays associated with full FOM evaluations. This approach mitigates local minima in Figure 13 and improves high-error cases such as that in Figure 15b. Alternatively, by adjusting the weighting scheme between competing attributes, the framework can prioritize efficiency and select the VpROM instead, as illustrated in Figure 14b.

Figure 16: Framework's acceleration response approximation at the redundant node and corresponding error bounds. The average and maximum error performance across testing samples is reported.

488 5. Discussion

490 The developed framework addresses a central challenge in real-time Operations and Management (O&M), Structural Health Monitoring (SHM), and decision support—the adaptive selection of the lowest-cost model capable of delivering predictions of the required fidelity under evolving conditions [4]. At its core, the proposed framework integrates a generative reduced-order modeling (ROM) scheme, conditioned on parametric inputs, with a Bayesian inference layer that recursively estimates the underlying system parameters from sensing data. This combination enables 492 continuous model adaptation, quantifies prediction confidence, and supports decision-making through a utility-based formulation that balances two competing attributes: (i) model fidelity and (ii) computational efficiency. By maximizing the expected utility, the framework identifies the fit-for-purpose model at each time step, determining whether to 494 accept, switch, or retrain a candidate representation.

498 Two numerical case studies—a hysteretic shear frame with uneven damage and a geometrically nonlinear fuselage panel—demonstrate the framework’s ability to select optimal model resolutions and adapt to changing system conditions. The approach reliably identifies when reduced-order models lose validity and retraining is required, particularly during extreme events beyond the training domain. Moreover, the probabilistic formulation provides uncertainty quantification, generating response confidence bounds that capture the true behavior even under low-precision conditions.

504 Several limitations outline avenues for future research. First, the current iTMCMC-based Bayesian updating remains computationally demanding for high-dimensional problems; future work will explore more efficient inference strategies for real-time deployment. Second, the framework assumes that all relevant physics are represented within the available models. A fully adaptive system should also handle unforeseen or unmodeled phenomena, where even high-fidelity models may yield low utility—a challenge pointing toward self-evolving digital representations. Third, while this study uses perturbed simulation data to avoid inverse crime, experimental validation will be essential to assess robustness in real-world conditions. Finally, the parametric formulations employed may not fully capture effects such as excitation frequency content or mode interactions; these aspects will be explored alongside the extension toward self-evolving model structures.

512 Data Availability

The models and data supporting this study’s findings are available from the author **KV** upon request.

514 Declaration of Competing Interest

516 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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744 **CRediT authorship contribution statement**

Konstantinos Vlachas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing. **Antonis Kamariotis:**
746 Methodology, Software. **Eleni Chatzi:** Resources, Writing - review & editing.